

Revamping Education for Sustainable Development: A Vision for New Future

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Abstract

Sustainability or durability means meeting the requirements of the present generation without compromising the demands of future generations. Which means using the things obtained from nature in such a way that the next generation won't have to make compromises. For this, we have to use the natural resources as per the need and requirement to protect them. As we all know that nature has immense reserves of resources on this earth and if we use all those things well, then we will save our resources. Because if there is a lack of resources for the coming generation, they may have to face a lot of trouble and problems in life. The way the population is increasing, if we do not use natural resources like coal, water, gas, etc. well, then the coming generation will get to hear only its name. Education is known as a great power.

A power that contributes not only to the development of the nation but also to sustainable development. Education is such a process, through which social, economical and personal development is possible. It promotes the cognition and expertise needed for the sustainability of resources. India is well known as the globally largest democratic country and India has also conducted many beneficial schemes and programs within the country for sustainability so that the process of sustainable development in the country can be accelerated. Apart from this, India has also signed several agreements with the international community.

Keywords: Education, sustainable Development, ESD, Future, Generation, Resources

Introduction

Sustainability or durability means meeting the requirements of the present generation without compromising the demands of future generations which means using the things obtained from nature in such a way that the next generation won't have to make compromises. For this, we have to use the natural resources as per the need and requirement to protect them.

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Education is known as a great power. A power that contributes not only to the development of the nation but also to sustainable development. Education is such a process, through which social, economical and personal development is possible. It promotes the cognition and expertise needed for the sustainability of resources.

It also requires collaborative learning and innovative teaching strategies that motivate & capacitate students to change their attitudes & behaviours and make their contributions to sustainable development. Revamping education for the sustainability & development therefore, fosters

proficiencies among learners such as critical awareness, visualizing subsequent scenarios, & cooperative decisiveness.

Concept of Sustainability & Development

The Council of the European Union explains in 2010 that ESD is preferred in the semi-formal and informal educational systems as well as at all the phases of formal instruction and education, since it is required to create a sustainable society.

Sustainable Development Education Panel Report, 1998 explains the need for Education for Sustainability and development,

“The learning required to maintain & enhance both our standard and the quality of posterity is what Sustainability and development are all about. The ability to contribute in decisions about how we act collectively & individually locally & universally, which will enhance the standard of living without harming the earth for the next generations is made possible by ESD.”

Based on the above definitions we can explain that sustainable development is a development in which we use the resources present in nature according to our needs in such a way that the resources can be saved for the use of the next generations.

We all should use the resources according to our needs. One great person has said that everything on this earth is sufficient to meet everyone's needs, but few human beings have misused it. It means that we should supply our needs, not greed. Sustainable development is to use the resources in sufficient quantity and to save for the coming generations.

Modernization has badly injured the natural resources, as a result of which the present and future generations may have to bear the consequences, so governments are now giving more importance to sustainable development, so that future generations can also lead a happy life with natural resources.

In the words of **Pearce and Barford**- “Sustainable development is a process in which the natural resource base is not allowed to deplete. It emphasizes the hitherto unappreciated role of environmental quality and environmental inputs in the process of increasing real income and quality of life.”

Pillars of Sustainable Development

The three sustainability foundations serve as a useful framework for describing the problem of sustainability & development. The economical, societal, and environmental foundations are 3 parts of this. The global society cannot be sustained as a whole if even one foundation is weak. The following figure represents the three pillars/foundations:

Figure 1- Pillars of Sustainability

Environmental Pillar

Environment-related sustainability is, how well the environment can support the mentioned ranges of herbal beneficial resource extraction rates indefinitely. It is the actual confrontation on

the earth, but the longer the repercussion of not dissolving the problem is postponed, the lower the priority it gets to solve the problem.

In this, we have to focus our attention on the problems related to the environment, such as air, water, and other disorders related to the environment. Thus keeping the environment healthy for the benefit of mankind should be our priority.

Societal Pillar

Social sustainability includes, among other key societal elements, the security of natural resources, morality, human life, safety, and literacy. Advancing society Economic and environmental benefits should also be encouraged by efforts to promote social sustainability benefits. Increased social sustainability has a positive impact on the environment. The environment can gain from campaigning for healthier eating patterns because, for instance, people's dietary choices and habits can have a large positive impact on encompassing both environmental and human well-being.

Social sustainability emphasizes ideas like cohesion, reciprocity, the necessity of honesty and interpersonal interactions, as well as maintaining and enhancing social quality. It can be encouraged and supported by norms, education, and a shared concept of liberty and impartiality. Social sustainability includes the idea of sustainability and development as described by the Sustainable Development aim of the United.Nations

Economical Pillar

Capital protection is the main objective of economic sustainability. Economical conservation and sustainability seek to raise living standards, whereas societal conservation sustainability focuses on increasing social fairness and equal opportunities. It denotes to the effective utilization of assets in the reference of business to maintain long-term corporate profitability. The UK gov't's Annual Report 2000, which was released in January 2001, explains "one of the fundamental goals of sustainability and development is to maintain consistently high GDP growth rates. Economic development cannot be stopped but, a sustainable process moves beyond growth in the economy. Growth matters, both in regards to quality & quantity."

Businesses, governments, and organizations have assimilated the three pillars into their venture since the 1980s, when they first obtained universal popularity, with varied degrees of success. True sustainability, theoretically speaking, prerequisite even take into account the 3 pillars.

Role of Education for Sustainability and Development

Quality-assured education is a crucial tool for building a more sustainable & environment- friendly future. It was highlighted at the United Nations World Summit in 2002 at Johannesburg, where it was said that "Revamping the nation's scholastic and learning programmes was the necessary requirement for attaining sustainability and development. Education for Sustainability and Development, which fosters the growth of the wisdom, competencies, comprehension, values, and behaviour patterns needed for building a sustainable world, aims to ensure environmental preservation and restoration, advance social equity, and promote economic stability." An important factor in the creation of the concept of education for sustainability and development was environmental education, which attempted to deliver individuals with the information, skills, principles, beliefs, and conducts required to conserve resources. Education for sustainability seeks to empower people to make decisions and act to improve the quality of their lives without sacrificing anything.

According to UNESCO," The aim of the decade is to incorporate sustainable development's guiding ideas, ethics, and implementations into each facet of pedagogy and learning. This strives to promote behavioural modifications that will lead to a future that is more sustainable". Recognizing the necessity of including a great variety of contributors from the public, trade sector, civic organizations, non-government organizations, & government is one of the most crucial elements of Education for sustainability.

With the help of sustainable development education, our future can be changed. The present worldwide environmental issues can be settled with the devoted efforts of the government, suitable rules & regulations, reliable behaviour on the part of people and societies, and mostly a deep sense of concern for the sustainability of the environment. The scope of this type of education goes outside the school environment. The lessons a child picks up during this phase shouldn't stop there; the parents should also apply whatever they've studied. Utilizing resources such as water and power energy effectively at home as well as at work must be a component of our inherent conduct as parents and carers. Being environmentally conscious is only one component of education for sustainability and development; it also calls for the development of leadership, communication, and managerial abilities. All of above-mentioned qualities are essential for personal development. Giving young people these useful abilities in addition to their environmental awareness and understanding will help them succeed in leading lives that advance humanity and respect and care for our earth's natural resources.

Therefore, education for sustainable development encourages research and offers the knowledge necessary to address issues with sustainable development that result from human-made decisions. Investing in education as a human resource is one of the key elements that make sustainable development possible.

Revamping Education for Sustainability and Development

Education's role in promoting sustainability and development was recognized by the global community at the turn of the twenty-first century. It is now widely believed that we must start promoting via education the behaviours, lifestyle, and habits prerequisite for future sustainability. Our lifestyles and behaviour are significantly influenced by education for sustainable development. Making judgments that influence us is something we learn how to do through education. It is concerned about how the economic, ecology and social well-being of all communities would develop in the 156 areas of health, education, and food security. One of the main goals of education is to develop the ability for this kind of forward-looking thinking.

It's a fresh approach to education. This vision supports the realisation of this educational objective within the framework of sustainable development by individuals of all ages. It aids pupils in gaining a greater understanding of the society in which they live, learns and play.

This view of education emphasizes changes in attitudes, behaviour, and thinking as well as a comprehensive, integrated, and multidisciplinary approach to the development of wisdom and expertise needed for future sustainability. In order to empower people (especially young) to determine and act in culturally acceptable and locally relevant ways to address and repair the environmental challenges that threaten our shared future, we must redirect the educational curriculum to programmes, policies, and practices.

Therefore, a country's ability to develop and meet sustainability goals depends on basic education. Basic education can raise women's status, boost agricultural output, slow down population growth, and increase living conditions and environmental protection. According to The Economic Times, 2020, the pandemic has made it clear that India Inc. needs to prioritize sustainability at the top of its agenda.

Sustainability and Development: An Indian Perspective

India has made a number of steps to fulfil all objectives and maintain its development. The Swachh Bharat project, which promotes sanitation and cleanliness, as well as the National Mission for Green India, Namami Gange Program, Compensatory Afforestation Fund Management and Planning Authority (CAMPA), and green skill development programme, are examples of proactive activities. Additionally, there are national river management initiatives and plans for preserving ecosystems and natural resources.

India is making great efforts to put the sustainable development strategy into practice. Since 2015, the Indian government has introduced a number of noteworthy and successful initiatives aimed at

achieving Sustainable development Goals (SDGs). India has long encouraged sustainable development by involving numerous stakeholders.

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